

Building the Legal Knowledge Graph for Smart Compliance Services in Multilingual Europe

Welcome to the **Webinar Special Issue of the Lynx Newsletter!** During the months of December 2020 to February 2021, we conducted the **Lynx Webinar Series**, presenting the project and its most outstanding achievements to SMEs, LegalTech companies and the public.

The **first webinar** provided an overview of and insights in the Lynx project, the Legal Knowledge Graph and its application to Lynx, and the Lynx architecture, services and pilots. The **second webinar** provided insights into the compliance services related to the three pilots of Lynx and their objectives, requirements and technical solutions in the domains of labour law, contract analysis and management, and geothermal energy compliance recommender. The **third webinar** focused on a technical audience, providing insights into the overall architecture of the Lynx Services Platform and details and demos of the basic services: document manager, workflow manager, API manager, and authorization & identity management. On top of that, the **fourth webinar** demonstrated these services: Named Entity Extraction, Relation Extraction, Question-Answering, Machine Translation and Lexicala cross-lingual lexical data.

The **Lynx YouTube channel** contains all the recordings of the Lynx Webinar Series as well as demos for the Time Extraction and Entity Linking Services. Moreover, the **Slideshare channel** stores the slide decks used in the four webinars.

Please take a look at the newsletter for more information on the webinars and follow us on our social media channels to stay posted on the pilots release.

Thank you for your attention.

The Lynx consortium

[Lynx YouTube channel](#)[Lynx Slideshare channel](#)

Lynx Webinar Series

To bring the project itself as well as the results to our specified target audiences, the Lynx consortium conducted the Lynx Webinar Series during the months of December 2020 and February 2021.

The following webinars were held:

1. Webinar 1: Lynx overall introduction

When: 10.12.2020, 10.30am CET (1 hour)

Slides: <https://www.slideshare.net/Lyn...>

Recording: <https://youtube.com/playlist?l...>

2. Webinar 2: 3 Business Cases on top of the Lynx Legal Knowledge Graph

When: 14.1.2021, 10.30am CET (1 hour)

Slides: <https://www.slideshare.net/Lyn...>

Recording: <https://youtube.com/playlist?l...>

3. Webinar 3: The Lynx Services Platform (LySP) - Part 1: Overview

When: 11/02/2021, 11.30am CET (1 hour)

Slides: <https://www.slideshare.net/Lyn...>

Recording: <https://youtube.com/playlist?l...>

4. Webinar 4: The Lynx Services Platform (LySP) - Part 2: The Services

When: 18/02/2021, 10.30am CET (1 hour)

Slides: <https://www.slideshare.net/Lyn...>

Recording: <https://youtube.com/playlist?l...>

Webinar #1: Compliance made easy

The main objective of the Lynx research and innovation project is to create an ecosystem of smart cloud services to better manage compliance, based on a Legal

Knowledge Graph (LKG) that integrates and links multilingual and heterogeneous compliance data sources including legislation, case law, standards, regulations and other private contracts, besides others.

The **first webinar** provided an overview of and insights in the Lynx project, the Legal Knowledge Graph and its application to Lynx, and the Lynx architecture, services and pilots.

- **The Lynx project.** Elena Montiel Ponsoda, Lynx project lead, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
- **Legal Knowledge Graph: What is this & what is it good for.** Martin Kaltenböck, Lynx Innovation Manager, Co-Founder and CFO of Semantic Web Company, SWC
- **The Lynx Legal Knowledge Graph Model.** Victor Rodriguez Doncel, Lynx Scientific Manager, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
- **Lynx Services Platform (LySP): Architecture & Services.** Artem Revenko, Director of Research & Innovation, SWC
- **The 3 Pilots of Lynx: labor law, contract management, geothermal energy compliance.** Christian Sageder, Managing Director, Cybly GmbH

Lynx Webinar #1 Recording

Webinar #2: 3 Business Cases

The **second webinar** provided insights into the compliance services related to the three pilots of Lynx and their objectives, requirements and technical solutions in the domains of labour law, contract analysis and management, and geothermal energy compliance recommender.

- **Moderation:** Martin Kaltenböck (Co-Founder and CFO of Semantic Web Company, SWC)
- **Introduction:** Elena Montiel-Ponsoda (Lynx project lead, Ontology Engineering Group, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)
- **Labor law Pilot, Cuatrecasas,** Pascual Boil (Consultancy and Applications Director at CUATRECASAS)
- **Contract Analysis Pilot, Cybly,** Christian Sageder (Managing Director at Cybly GmbH)
- **Geothermal Energy Compliance, DNV.GL,** Pieter Verhoeven (Senior Consultant / Digital Innovation Manager at DNV GL)

Lynx Webinar #2 Recording

Webinar #3: Lynx Services Platform (LySP) Overview

The **third webinar** focused on a technical audience, providing insights into the overall architecture of the Lynx Services Platform and details and demos of the basic services: document manager, workflow manager, API manager, and authorization & identity management.

- **Introduction & Moderation:** Martin Kaltenböck (Co-Founder and CFO of Semantic Web Company, SWC)
- **LySP Architecture,** Filippo Maganza (Software Developer at Alpenite) and Sotiris Karampatakis (Senior Researcher at Semantic Web Company)
- **LySP Basic Services,** Filippo Maganza (Software Developer at Alpenite) and Victor Mireles-Chavez (Senior Researcher at Semantic Web Company)

Summarization Service (1)

Extractive summarisation

- TF-IDF
 - Cluster models
 - Encode documents
- Centroids and composability of word embeddings
 - Extract keywords and concepts
 - Project sentence in embedding space

Relevance scores (distance to centroid) Filter

Webinar #4: Lynx Services Platform (LySP) - The Services

The **fourth webinar** demonstrated these services: Named Entity Extraction, Relation Extraction, Question-Answering, Machine Translation and Lexicala cross-lingual lexical data.

- **Introduction & Moderation:** Martin Kaltenböck (Co-Founder and CFO of Semantic Web Company, SWC)
- **LySP Services - Introduction and Overview,** Artem Revenko (Director of Research & Innovation, Semantic Web Company)
- **LySP Services,** Ruben Martinez (Manager Customer Service, Tilde), Ilan Kernerman (CEO at Lexicala by K Dictionaries), Christian Sageder (CEO of Cybly), Victor Mireles-Chavez (Senior Researcher, SWC), Julian Moreno (Researcher at DFKI), Victor Rodriguez Doncel (Assistant Lecturer, Artificial Intelligence Department, UPM).

Consortium

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780602

**Institute of Law and Technology - Universitat
Autònoma de Barcelona**

Faculty of Law, B Building. Campus UAB, Cerdanyola del
Valles
Spain

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